

Studies on the Citrate Complexes of Magnesium and Barium

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The citrate complexes of magnesium and barium have been studied by *pH*-titration method. The anionic complexes are of 1:1 type. The magnesium and barium complexes are formed according to the equations:

The formation constants of the magnesium citrate and barium citrate complexes are 4.39×10^3 and 4.32×10^3 respectively.

Hastings¹ determined the stability constant of magnesium citrate complex by biological assay method and found it to be 1.59×10^3 . Joseph² determined the formation constant of Ba-citrate complex by electrode-potential method and found it to be 9.550×10^2 and 1.047×10^3 .

EXPERIMENTAL

An *M/20* barium perchlorate solution was prepared in a manner similar to the preparation of calcium perchlorate solution³. Four *pH*-titrations, performed to investigate the formation of magnesium and barium citrate complexes, are recorded in Table I

TABLE I

Temp.	Solutions titrated.		Soln. conc. used.	Results.	
	Volume.	Contents. *Conc.			
		Expt. I.			
32.5°	200 m.e.	Ct	0.0250	<i>N</i> -NaOH	Curve A, Fig. 1.
32.5°	200	Ct	0.0250	..	Curve B, Fig. 1.
		MgSO ₄	0.0025		
		Expt. II.			
35.5°	100	NaClO ₄	0.0250	0.1 <i>M</i> Na citrate	Curve A, Fig. 2.
32.5°	100	NaClO ₄	0.0250	..	Curve B, Fig. 2.
		MgSO ₄	0.00125		
		Expt. III.			
32°	200	Ct	0.0250	<i>N</i> -NaOH	Curve A, Fig. 3.
32°	200	Ct	0.0250	..	Curve B, Fig. 3.
		Be(ClO ₄) ₂	0.0025		
		Expt. IV.			
32°	100	NaClO ₄	0.0250	0.1 <i>M</i> Na citrate	Curve A, Fig. 4.
32°	100	NaClO ₄	0.0250	..	Curve B, Fig. 4.
		Ba(ClO ₄) ₂	0.00125		

N.B. Ct denotes citric acid.

*Expressed in g. mole.

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1. *J. Biol. Chem.*, 1934, **107**, 351.

2. *Ibid.*, 1946, **164**, 529.

3. Patnaik and Pani, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 229.

DISCUSSION

The results obtained in experiments I-IV are similar to those obtained in similar experiments with calcium and strontium citrate complexes⁴. In experiments I and III, the horizontal distance between the curves increases in the beginning and then decreases, and finally becomes negligible after pH 6.0.

NaOH added in ml.

FIG. 1

0.1M Sodium citrate added in ml.

FIG. 2

The number of citrate ligands bound per metal ions can be determined from these experiments. Since the amount of citric acid is large, the horizontal distance indicates the amount of total citrate ligand bound due to the formation of a complex at that pH. Let 'x' and 'y' be two points on the same pH axis on the curve A and B, respectively. If $[Ct]_x$, $[Ct]_y$, and $[metal\ salt]$ represent respectively the molar concentrations of total citrate at 'x', total citrate at 'y', and metal salt $MgSO_4$ or $Ba(ClO_4)_2$ at 'y', the number of ligands bound per metal ion ($\bar{n}$) can be expressed as:

$$\bar{n} = \frac{[Ct]_x - [Ct]_y}{[Metal\ salt]}$$

$[Ct]_x$, $[Ct]_y$, and $[metal\ salt]$ are calculated as before. $\bar{n}$ values calculated for magnesium citrate complexes are 0.25, 0.5, and 0.22 at pH 2.0, 4.3, and 5.0 respectively. Since values of $\bar{n}$ never exceed 0.5, a complex of 1:1 type is indicated.

The values of $\bar{n}$ determined for barium citrate complexes are 0.17, 0.19 and 0.17 at pH 3.0, 4.6, and 5.4 respectively. This confirms also a 1:1 type complex. In experiments II and IV, the pH of the system 'B' containing magnesium or barium is lower than those of the system 'A'. This indicates the removal of citrate ions by Mg^{2+} or Ba^{2+} ions due to formation of a complex. A change in the nature of rise in curve B comes after the addition of very nearly 1 g. mole of sodium citrate/g. mole of magnesium sulphate and barium perchlorate indicates the formation of a 1:1 complex. The reactions

in experiments II and IV can be represented by equation (1) and equilibrium constant, by equation (1-1):

$$\frac{[M Cit^{-}]}{[M^{2+}] [Cit^{3-}]} = K \quad \dots (1-1)$$

(M^{2+} represents Mg^{2+} or Ba^{2+} ions)

$[Ct]_A$, $[Ct]_B$, $[MgSO_4]$, $[Ba(ClO_4)_2]$, $[MgCit^{-}]$, $[BaCit^{-}]$, $[Cit^{3-}]$, $[Mg^{2+}]$, and $[Ba^{2+}]$ are calculated from experiments II and IV, as determined in the case of calcium citrate complex. The values obtained are recorded in Tables II and III for magnesium and barium, respectively. The values of K are 4.39×10^3 and 4.32×10^2 for magnesium citrate and barium citrate complexes, respectively.

N-NaOH added in ml.
FIG. 3

0.1M Sodium citrate added in ml.
FIG. 4

TABLE II

pH.	$[Ct]_A$ or $[Cit^{3-}] \times 10^4$.	$[Ct]_B \times 10^3$.	$[MgSO_4] \times 10^2$.	$[MgCit^{3-}] \times 10^3$.	$[Mg^{2+}] \times 10^3$.	$K \times 10^{-3}$.
6.93	0.4097	1.961	1.226	1.912	10.35	3.697
6.94	0.9988	2.724	1.216	2.625	9.54	2.755
6.95	0.9988	3.661	1.204	3.562	8.48	4.205
6.96	1.1990	4.791	1.191	4.599	7.32	5.242
6.97	1.4970	5.304	1.184	5.155	6.69	5.145
6.98	1.7480	5.838	1.177	5.664	6.11	5.309

TABLE III

pH.	$[Ct]_A$ or $[Cit^{3-}] \times 10^4$.	$[Ct]_B \times 10^3$.	$[Ba(ClO_4)_2] \times 10^2$.	$[BaCit^{-}] \times 10^3$.	$[Ba^{2+}] \times 10^2$.	$K \times 10^{-2}$.
7.200	0.9988	0.7938	1.240	0.6940	1.171	5.933
7.230	1.9950	0.8921	1.239	0.6926	1.170	2.966
7.250	1.9950	0.9902	1.278	0.7906	1.159	3.419
7.2650	2.4960	1.3800	1.233	1.1310	1.120	4.049
7.2650	2.990	1.6610	1.226	1.6620	1.060	5.242

The citrate complexes of the alkaline earth metals are of mainly ionic type; hence the stability of the complexes increases with increasing ionic charge and decreasing ionic radius of the metal ions.

From the values of the stability constant K of the citrate complexes of the alkaline earth metals, it can be inferred that the stability of the complexes decreases in the order of Mg, Ca, Sr, Ba.

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